

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ON THE PROCESS OF CHARGE CARRIER DRIFT ON RECOMBINATION CENTERS IN SEMICONDUCTORS

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Abstract

The paper discusses the process of charge carrier drift on recombination centers in semiconductors. The process consists in the fact that the interaction with recombination centers of charge carriers does not disappear, but on the contrary they change their direction, and participate in conductivity. Such behavior of charge carriers by recombination centers or this process was called the "Bohr-Omon" effect.

Keywords: recombination centers, charge carriers, semiconductors, polycrystalline silicon, temperature, concentration of charge carriers, region of grain boundaries.

Introduction

At present, the interaction of recombination centers with charge carriers in semiconductors can be considered to be fairly well studied from both experimental and theoretical points of view (see, for example, [1-10] and references cited therein). It has been reliably established that the interaction of recombination centers with charge carriers in polycrystalline silicon is characterized by a stepwise change in the mobility and concentration of charge carriers in the temperature range of $\sim 20\text{--}500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [2-4], as a result of which their total concentration of charge carriers is determined by the concentration of charge carriers (n_2), captured by recombination centers associated with impurity states and defects in the region of grain boundaries. In the successive manifestation of recombination centers at energy levels, for example, $E\sim 0.15\text{ eV}$, $E\sim 0.17\text{ eV}$, $E\sim 0.3\text{ eV}$ and $E\sim 0.36\text{ eV}$, and the increase in captured charge carriers at these levels leads to an increase in n_2 , while the total concentration of charge carriers in polycrystalline silicon materials decreases and vice versa, a decrease leads to an increase in the total concentration of charge carriers [2-4]. This process leads to a decrease in the efficiency of semiconductor devices and solar cells [1-10]. As for the process of drift of charge carriers on recombination centers, it is an unsolved problem. Although the effects of recombination centers on the transfer of charge carriers in semiconductors have been studied quite well [1-10]. The current problem is to study the mechanism and process of drift of charge carriers on recombination centers in semiconductors. This work is devoted to the study of the mechanism and process of drift of charge carriers on recombination centers and their influence on thermoelectric properties in thermoelectric generators based on semiconductor thermoelements.

Model of structure and mechanism of charge transfer

It is known that a thermoelectric generator based on semiconductor thermoelements connected to each other in series or parallel directly converts thermal energy into electrical energy. In a thermoelectric generator, the Seebeck effect is used to generate electricity, which consists in the appearance of an electromotive

force in a closed circuit of two dissimilar materials if the contact points are maintained at different temperatures. The effect occurs because the energies of free electrons or holes in a semiconductor material depend on temperature. If there is a temperature gradient along the semiconductor during heat supply Q , then the charge carriers at the hot end (A) acquire higher energies and speeds than at the cold end (B); in semiconductors, in addition to this, the concentration of conductivity charge carriers increases with temperature. As a result, a flow of charge carriers from the hot end (A) to the cold end (B) occurs (as shown in Fig. 1a), and as a result, a current arises in the closed circuit. Fig. 1 shows the zone diagram of a thermoelectric generator based on semiconductor thermoelements. It can be conditionally divided into several sections, as shown in Fig. 1. It should also be noted that to estimate the flow or drift of charge carriers on recombination centers, we use the results obtained in [2-4], i.e. we accept the following condition: manifestation of recombination centers on energy levels, for example, $E\sim 0.15\text{ eV}$ energy level appears at $T_2\sim 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and at $T_3\sim 70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ this level disappears and a new level $E\sim 0.17\text{ eV}$ appears, sequentially this level also disappears and a new level $E\sim 0.3\text{ eV}$ appears at $T_4\sim 100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and also at $T_5\sim 250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ this level disappears and a new level $E\sim 0.36\text{ eV}$ appears. In such cases, the flow of charge carriers can be put in the following sequences:

1. In the initial heating process, for example, if the temperature in section I changes $T_1 < 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a flow of charge carriers occurs from the hot end (A) to the cold end (B), through the component sections II, III, IV, V and VI, respectively (Fig. 1a), as a result of which a current arises in the closed circuit.

2. With increasing energy of heat Q , if the temperature is $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C} < T_2 < 70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on section I, and on section II increases to $T_1 < 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, then recombination centers with $E\sim 0.15\text{ eV}$ are observed on section I. In this case, the heat generated by charge carriers is captured at these levels. If their concentration is greater than the concentration of charge carriers on section II, then a flow of charge carriers towards section I is observed. That is, capture at levels $E\sim 0.15\text{ eV}$ can occur (Fig. 1b). In this

process, the direction of the flow of charge carriers changes from end (B) to end (A).

3. If the temperature in section I is $70^{\circ}\text{C} < T_3 > 100^{\circ}\text{C}$, and in section II in the range $50^{\circ}\text{C} < T_2 > 70^{\circ}\text{C}$, and in section III increases to $T_1 < 50^{\circ}\text{C}$, then recombination centers are observed at $E \sim 0.17\text{ eV}$ in section I, and at $E \sim 0.15\text{ eV}$ in section II. In this case, the heat generated by charge carriers in section I and section II is captured at the levels of $E \sim 0.17\text{ eV}$ and $E \sim 0.15\text{ eV}$, respectively. As was said above, their concentration is greater than the heat generated by charge carriers in section III, then a flow or drift of charge carriers is observed towards section I and section II at these levels (Fig. 1c). In this process, the direction of the flow of charge carriers from end (B) to end (A) continues.

4. If the temperature changes in section I, II, and III respectively $100^{\circ}\text{C} < T_4 > 250^{\circ}\text{C}$, $70^{\circ}\text{C} < T_3 > 100^{\circ}\text{C}$,

$50^{\circ}\text{C} < T_3 > 70^{\circ}\text{C}$, and recombination centers are observed respectively at the following energy levels, for example, $E \sim 0.3\text{ eV}$ and $E \sim 0.17\text{ eV}$ and $E \sim 0.15\text{ eV}$, and the temperature in section IV increases to $T_1 < 50^{\circ}\text{C}$. In this case, a flow or drift of charge carriers occurs (Fig. 1e, 1f, 1g and 1h) as stated in paragraph 3. Also in this case, the direction of the flow of charge carriers from end (B) to end (A) continues. This process occurs until the disappearance of the recombination centers. For example, in the work [2-4] we discovered a decrease in the influence of recombination centers on the transfer of charge carriers at $>300^{\circ}\text{C}$. Consistently with the disappearance of recombination centers in sections I, II, III, respectively, a change in the direction of the flow of charge carriers occurs from end (A) to end (B).

Fig. 1. Band diagram of a thermoelement based on semiconductors and the mechanism and process of charge carrier drift with the participation of recombination centers.

Conclusions

Thus, in semiconductors, the captured charge carriers on the recombination centers do not participate in conductivity. In this case, there is no flow of charge carriers and as a result, in a closed circuit, no current is observed in thermoelectric generators based on semiconductor thermoelements. However, in our cases, the occurrence and switching of current and voltage under the above conditions was experimentally detected [2]. In our opinion, in the process of interaction with recombination centers, charge carriers do not disappear, on the contrary, they participate in conductivity. This process can be presented as a fight between charge carriers and recombination centers. In the fight against recombination centers, charge carriers do not disappear, on the contrary, as they say in Uzbek, "omon koladi - will

survive", and participate in conductivity, i.e., in order to participate in conductivity, they change their direction. Such behavior of charge carriers with recombination centers can be called the "Bor-Omon" effect. That is, we called such behavior of charge carriers with recombination centers the "Bor-Omon" effect. Here, Bor – is the fight against recombination centers by charge carriers, Omon – is not the disappearance of charge carriers.

References

1. Polycrystalline semiconductors. Physical properties and applications: Trans. from English // Ed. Harbek G. Mir. Moscow, (1989) 344 p.

2. Olimov L.O. Inter Grain boundaries in polycrystalline silicon: microstructure, charge states and p-n transitions, //Doctor diss., 2016.
3. L.O. Olimov. The grain boundary model in pn structures based on polycrystalline semiconductors. *Geliotexnika*; (№2); p. 39-43 (2010) https://inis.iaea.org/search/search.aspx?orig_q=RN:42107435.
4. L.O. Olimov, B.M. Abdurakhmanov, A.Teshaboev. Effect of alkali metal atoms on charge carrier transport in the region of intergrain boundaries of polycrystalline silicon. *Materials Science*. 1 (2014) P.: 14-17. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=21034729>.
5. L.O. Olimov, I.T. Khojimatov. Thermoelectric properties of silicon oxide. *Journal E3S Web of Conferences* 458, 01022 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202345801022>.
6. L.O. Olimov, I.T. Khojimatov. Magnetic properties of substances. *Journal Scientific progress* 3(2), (2023). pp.357-359. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/magnetic-properties-of-substances>.
7. R. Aliyev, E. Mukhtarov, L. Olimov. Non-destructive method for measuring the pn-junction depth of semiconductor photovoltaic structures. *Physical Surface Engineering*. Vol. 8, No. 2. Pp. 169-172. (2010) <http://dspace.nbu.gov.ua/handle/123456789/98867>.
8. L. O. Olimov, E. Q. Mukhtarov, F. Abdurazaqov, Sh. Q. Kuchkanov. 2010. 5(1). https://inis.iaea.org/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/41/086/41086898.pdf.
9. Abdurazzakov, F. S., Zainabidinov, S. Z., Abdurakhmanov, B. M. et al. Influence of temperature on certain properties of n +p and n +p-p + structures based on secondary cast polycrystalline silicon. *Appl. Sol. Energy* 47, 149–151 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0003701X11020046>.
10. R. Aliyev, E. Mukhtarov, L. Olimov. The effective design of photoelectric generator. *Respublikanskaya konferentsiya Nukus (Uzbekistan)*; 23-25 Nov 2011 https://inis.iaea.org/search/search.aspx?orig_q=RN:43127493.
11. A.Teshaboev, S.Zaynobidinov, I.N. Karimov, L.O. Olimov. Evaluation of new laws in the grain boundaries associated with the incoming states. *National Conference Nukus (Uzbekistan)*; 1(11) C.23-25 Nov 2011 https://inis.iaea.org/search/search.aspx?orig_q=RN:43127503